

The effect of instructors at higher education institutions and the university environments on students' Adaptation to the field of physical education and sports.

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to ascertain how students' adjustment to the realm of sport and physical education is influenced by the university setting and the instructors at the teachers' higher college. We employed the descriptive method in this process, using a sample of fifty pupils. Results indicate that a well-equipped university setting and appropriate infrastructure have a positive impact on students' ability to adapt. Additionally, enhancing interaction during sessions is greatly influenced by the teachers' relationship with the students as well as their academic and psychological support. To enhance the educational process, the study suggests expanding resources and strengthening the bond between students and teachers.

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I. Introduction

The university environment is a key factor that highly affects the students' adaptation with their academic fields, as it is a comprehensive system that includes material and moral factors, not a mere space for education and training. The importance of this environment increases in the specialized institutions, such as in the teacher's higher colleges, as it builds the students' professional abilities to suit the future professional requirements (Aissaoui, 2022).

It plays a basic role in the field of sport and physical education, as it needs balance between the practical side, which needs physical performance and motor skills, and the theoretical side, which requires a deep understanding of the psychological and scientific concepts related to sports. Thus, the students' adaptation with this field is a complicated process that requires a suitable university environment that supports them academically and psychologically, and provides teachers who can support and guide them. Most of the students who choose this field aim at getting future jobs in sport and physical education, what adds a practical and academic dimension to this field.

The role of the university environment exceeds providing the academic facilities and covers the social and psychological factors that foster the sense of belonging and students' trust. In addition, the teachers are guides who provide the academic and psychological support needed in the phase of adaptation (Bouزيد, 2021). Literature review shows that these factors affect the students' adaptation. In this regard, the study of Brown et al. (2017) showed that the quality of sport facilities and infrastructure in the university environment play a key role in improving the students' adaptation with the sport fields. Besides, Harrison & Louis (2015) showed an effect for the educational curricula and sport activities on helping students better adapt, and that the academic and social support has a vital role. In addition, the study of Thomson & Ford (2019) proved that the social interaction between the students and their teachers' support foster the ability to face challenges.

Based on what was said, we raise the following problematic, "to what extent do the university environment and the relation with the teachers at the teachers' higher college affect the students' adaptation in the field of sport and physical education?"

2. Tools and methods:

2.1. The study population and sample:

It includes the 1st year students majoring in sport and physical education at the Teachers' Higher College of Laghouat. It is suitable for the study because the 1st year students are in the start of the academic and professional training, what allows us to examine the effect of the training programs and sport facilities on the quality of training since its early phases.

We used the purposive strategy to select the sample. To guarantee a good and accurate representation of the population, it includes 50 first-year male and female students.

2.2 The study procedures:

2.2.1. Method of the study:

We used the descriptive method, as it suits the study.

2.2.2. The study variables:

The university setting is the independent variable, while the students enrolled in physical education and sport education are the independent variables.

2.3. The study limitations:

2.3.1. The temporal limitations: The academic year 2023-2024.

2.3.2. The spatial limitations: The department of sport and physical education at the Higher College of Teachers in Laghouat

2.3.3. The human limitations: The 1st year students majoring in sport and physical education at the Higher College of Teachers in Laghouat.

3. The study tools:

After studying the topic, reviewing the literature, and surveying the views of curricula designs experts, we decided that the best tool for data collection is the questionnaire. Our questionnaire has one axis on the effect of the university environment and teachers at the

teachers' higher college on the students' adaptation with the field of sport and physical education.

3.1. The scientific bases of the tool:

3.1.1. The interrater validity (the face validity):

We used the face validity, as we made a primary questionnaire of 20 items and presented it to 06 teachers specialized in sport and physical education and 02 teachers specialized in psychology to read each item and decide whether it measures what is needed. We deleted the items that got agreement rates lower than 80%, and took the remarks into consideration, either regarding the formulation or the topic. Thus, we had 12 items in the end.

3.2.2. The tool consistency:

Table 1. The coefficient of consistency of each axis and the total of the axes

Scope	Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Axis	12	0.792

Table 01 shows that Cronbach's Alpha for the axes of the tool is 0.792, which is high and shows the high consistency, validity, and credibility of the tool in testing the study hypotheses.

3.2.3. The intrinsic validity:

By computing the consistency coefficient's quadratic root, it can be statistically determined. It is the upper limit of the tool's validity. This equation is used to measure it:

The quadratic root of the consistency coefficient

$$r = \sqrt{0,792} = 0,889$$

Thus, the validity coefficient is 0.889 and is statistically significant. Therefore, the questionnaire has a high degree of validity and can be applied on the study sample.

3.2.4. The statistical methods:

SPSS.

Cronbach's alpha: It measures the consistency of the tool.

The percentages: It measures the percentages of the informants' answers.

Chi-square: It shows the statistical significance of the answers.

4. The results:

Table 2. The statistical processes

Items	Answers	Percentage %	Answers	Percentage %	Calculated Chi ²	Table Chi ²	Degree of freedom	Significance level
01	Yes	54	No	46	0.320	3.841	01	0.05
02	Yes	92	No	8	35.280	3.841	01	0.05
03	Yes	84	No	16	23.120	3.841	01	0.05
04	Yes	68	No	32	6.480	3.841	01	0.05
05	Yes	70	No	30	8.000	3.841	01	0.05
06	Yes	82	No	18	20.480	3.841	01	0.05
07	Yes	90	No	10	32.000	3.841	01	0.05
08	Yes	81	No	18	20.480	3.841	01	0.05
09	Yes	76	No	24	13.620	3.841	01	0.05
10	Yes	74	No	26	11.620	3.841	01	0.05
11	Yes	80	No	20	18.000	3.841	01	0.05
12	Yes	56	No	44	0.720	3.841	01	0.05

Figure 1. Graphs that represent the answers in percentage

Figure 1: Graphs illustrating the sample responses as percentages

We analyzed the results using the percentages, calculated χ^2 , and table χ^2 to evaluate the different aspects of training on sport and physical education. Regarding the availability of the necessary facilities for study, 54% of the informants tell that college provides them, with a value of calculated χ^2 of 0.320, which is less than χ^2 (3.841) and shows no statistical significance for the availability of necessary facilities. As for the focus on excellent educational content, 92% of the informants tell that the teachers focus on it, with a value of calculated χ^2 of 35.820, which exceeds table χ^2 (3.841) and shows a strong statistical significance for the quality of educational content. Besides, 84% confirm that the teachers use educational styles that encourage the efficient participation, with a value of calculated χ^2 of 23.120, which exceeds table χ^2 (3.841) and shows a strong statistical significance for the use of styles that encourage the educational process.

As for the practical training chances, 68% confirm their availability, with a value of calculated χ^2 of 6.480, which exceeds table χ^2 (3.841) and shows a statistical significance for the chances of practical training. As for the suitability of the sport activities to the students' needs, 70% tell that the activities organized by the college suit their educational needs, with a value of calculated χ^2 of 8.000, which is more than table χ^2 (3.841) and

shows the suitability of the activities to the students' needs. Concerning the effective and periodical assessment of students, 82% confirm that they are being periodically and efficiently assessed, with a value of calculated Chi^2 of 20.480, which exceeds table Chi^2 (3.841) It has a significant positive impact on the effective and regular evaluation.

For the relation with teachers and fostering adaptation, 90% confirm that the relation with the teacher's fosters adaptation with the field, with a value of calculated Chi^2 of 32.000, which exceeds table Chi^2 (3.841) and shows a positive effect for the relation on the adaptation. Concerning the academic support to develop skills, 81% tell that there is enough academic support from teachers to develop students' skills in physical education, with a value of calculated Chi^2 of 20.480, which exceeds table Chi^2 (3.841) and shows a statistical significance that confirms the existence of an academic support.

Regarding the effect of the school environment on motivation, 76% confirm that it positively affects their motivation to develop their skills in sports, with a value of calculated Chi^2 of 13.620, which exceeds table Chi^2 (3.841) and shows the effect of this environment on motivation. Concerning the suitable environment for the social interaction among students, 74% tell that college provides an environment that fosters the social interaction among them, with a value of calculated Chi^2 of 11.620, which exceeds table Chi^2 (3.841) and confirms the importance of the social interaction environment in fostering cooperation among students. For the moral support from teachers, 80% say that the teachers provide a moral support that helps adapt with the challenges of study, with a value of calculated Chi^2 of 18.000, which is more than table Chi^2 (3.841) and shows the effect of moral support on improving the students' experience. Finally, 56% of the informants tell that the general atmosphere helps excel in this field, with a value of calculated Chi^2 of 0.720, which is less than table Chi^2 (3.841) and shows a no statistical significance for the effect of the general atmosphere on the student's excellence.

5. Discussion:

Our findings show the big importance of educational and sport facilities in consolidating the academic adaptation of students majoring in sport and physical education. The equipped university environment that provides the suitable infrastructure directly contributes to the improvement of the students' experience and develops their sport and academic skills and abilities. According to the results, students who utilized the excellent facilities demonstrated a greater degree of adaptability to the demands of the sector.

These results agree with those of Brown et al. (2017), who confirmed that the quality of sport facilities and infrastructure plays a crucial role in facilitating the students' adaptation, mainly in the sport fields, and that the availability of complementary training facilities encourages students to exploit their full potentials and achieve the academic and sport success. As for the educational curricula and sport activities, our findings show that students feel that the provided activities and curricula suit their educational and training needs and improve their adaptation. This is confirmed by the study of Harrison & Louis (2015), which found out that the well-designed curricula that complement the sport activities are a pivotal factor that helps students adapt academically. Besides, the study showed the importance of academic and social support from teachers to enhance the students' experience. This goes with our results, which confirm the role of the good relation between teachers and students in fostering the adaptation with the field.

On the other side, our study tackled the social interaction amid students and showed that the mutual support and cooperation among students, and the moral and psychological support from teachers, are key factors that help adapt with the study challenges. This goes with the study of Thomson & Ford (2019), which showed that the social interaction and academic support foster the students' abilities to face the academic stress and better integrate in their educational environment.

Based on these findings, we deduce that improving the educational and training environment, including the facilities, the curricula, and the social and academic support is an effective strategy to foster the students' adaptation with their fields. These factors allow developing the academic

and sport skills, and contribute to success in the educational and professional careers.

6. Conclusion:

In the end, we reached conclusions that help understand the status-quo of training and education of sport and physical education at the teacher's higher college. In this regard, the educational system has strengths, such as the teachers' focus on providing quality content and use of methods that encourage the students' participation. Besides, the good relation between students and teachers improves the educational adaptation of the students. However, some aspects need improvement, such as the availability of sport facilities and the periodical update of the training programs. Besides, the provision of the suitable training environment and equipments is one of the challenges that need focus to improve the students' experience in the field.

In light of these findings, we will offer some suggestions aimed at enhancing the environment for sport and physical education training and instruction:

1. Improving and expanding the sport facilities: The higher education institution's instructors should concentrate on offering the resources required for the study of sports and physical education, including updating and expanding the sport facilities to meet the needs of the students.
2. Developing the educational curricula: It is important to regularly update the educational curricula to suit the modern educational methods and techniques in sport and physical education. It is necessary to make sure that the curricula provide diverse sport activities and practical skills that satisfy the students' needs.
3. Increasing the chances of practical training: It is necessary to provide more chances of practical training in the sport institutions and different clubs, and to integrate the field training in the study curricula to foster the practical experiences of the students.
4. Enforcing the relation between students and teachers: It is necessary to consolidate the relation between students and teachers to support the academic and personal adaptation of students.

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